

“Impressed by Reading”

Workshop Report

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Background and aims of the workshop

The Lorentz Workshop “Impressed by Reading - Measuring the impact” was held on 24-27 February 2025 at the Lorentz Center in Leiden. The overall aim of the workshop was to bring together researchers from a wide range of disciplines, all working in some way on investigating the impact of reading fiction on readers, and explore shared challenges and opportunities. A more specific aim was to start developing a roadmap of shared research questions and challenges and of steps we can take collaboratively to address those challenges.

Organizing committee and funding

This Workshop was generously funded by the Lorentz Center in Leiden, the Impact & Fiction project, the Golem project, and the Huygens Institute.

Programme

The programme of the Workshop was designed to reach its goals by combining short presentations with various group activities and assignments. This included

- collaboratively working on a vocabulary to define shared concepts and terminology,
- discussing specific topics and challenges in break-out groups combined with sessions to report back, and
- drafting a shared roadmap and presenting and discussing it.

The programme was also designed to create a community feeling among the participants by focusing on shared research challenges and identifying which challenges are best tackled collaboratively. Establishing a community is crucial for defining future research steps.

Presentations

There were a number of presentations during the workshop.

Marijn Koolen - *What can Online Reader Reviews Tell Us About the Impact of Novels?*

Marijn Koolen described the Impact & Fiction project and the question of how online book reviews can be used to investigate how readers describe their reading experiences. He identified four conceptual issues that make reviews challenging for studying reading impact.

First, reviewers are only a small subset of all readers, and probably not representative, reviews are heavily skewed towards popular authors and books, and towards prolific reviewers (whereas most readers never write a review, and of those who do, the vast majority write only one or two reviews). There are also big differences in the length of reviews (a single evaluative statement versus a review summarising the plot, the reading experience and providing a lengthy evaluation of the story, characters and writing) and in the writing style of the review (distanced versus emotional)

Second, reviews are influenced by the platforms they are published on. Reviews on platforms that focus on book selling and buying are different in nature than those on platforms that focus on cataloguing or book discussion.

Third, there are various theories of reading that present different reading types, from *interpretive* readers who discuss the text and the author from a distance, to *experiencing* readers, who blend aspects of the text with their own life and experiences. However, these reading types have mostly been derived from in-depth interviews with readers. One open question is whether these reading types can also be derived from online reviews and whether that results in the same or similar types.

Finally, fourth, there is a gap between the low-level features at the level of words and sentences that are easy to measure computationally and the high-level features that reviewers mention in their reviews, e.g. character development, plot twists, evocative writing or the social relevance of the themes.

Maria Antoniak - *Narrative Detection in Social Media*

Maria Antoniak described how storytelling can be detected in social media messages and how the fraction of a text in a social media post that is presented in the form of storytelling differs across platforms and subcommunities on those platforms. She described the development of an annotation codebook for annotating instances of storytelling in texts and the creation of the StorySeeker dataset¹ of 502 annotated Reddit posts, which was used to finetune an LLM to

¹ <https://github.com/maria-antoniak/storyseeker>

detect such instances (Antoniak et al. 2024). The model annotated samples of 1000 messages for each of 291 subreddits. They found that subreddits with higher levels of self-disclosure have higher levels of storytelling. In future work, they want to look at the relationship between storytelling and community features such as trust, toxicity and dominant narratives.

Thomas Weitin - *Measuring the impact of literature on empathy and judgment*

Thomas Weitin presented findings from two studies. In the first study, the authors had participants read excerpts from the original Harry Potter books, as well as regular Harry Potter fanfiction and fanfiction that was deliberately poorly written (so-called Badfiction), while measuring brain activity using EEG. They found that frequent readers and readers familiar with a genre or story world show different brain activity from infrequent readers and readers not familiar to the genre or story world. The second study focused on the effects of literary fiction on high school students. In this study, students read stories while their levels of arousal and facial muscle activity were measured to capture when they experienced positive or negative emotions. The results lead to the findings that literature can foster empathy, and that students with a higher awareness of the historical context of literary texts are more confident in making judgements.

Tina Ternes - *Studying Shared Reading in Young Adults: Transcription and Analysis of Audio Recordings*

Shared reading can have a positive impact on mental well-being and on reading habits. Tina Ternes presented a study of shared reading among young adults (aged 18-25), as part of the SHARD-project.² Data was collected as video recordings of the sessions, as well as an interview and questionnaires presented before, immediately after and eight weeks after the reading sessions. The audio of the shared reading session and discussions is transcribed using Automatic Speech Recognition. The questionnaires include various validated scales such as the Predictors of Leisure Reading Scale (Martin-Chang et al., 2021) and an adapted version of the Reading Habits Questionnaire (Kuijpers, Douglas & Kuiken, 2020) and the newly developed Mechanisms of Shared Reading Questionnaire including the dimensions Absorption, Text- and Group Interaction, Interaction with the Reader Leader, and Compassion. The aim is to publish this dataset for future study.

Álvaro Ceballos Viro - *Poetry lovers of the past: topic modeling of private anthologies*

Álvaro Ceballos Viro presented a study of private anthologies in which people copied poems, in which he transcribed five anthologies from different persons and periods and compared them against the texts of several poets in the same periods. He looked at both word usage and topics across these anthologies, and found that the anthologies share semantic fields and are clearly distinguishable from the poets.

² www.shard-project.com

Ze Yu - Across the Pages: A Comparative Analysis of Reader Response to Web Novels in Different Languages

Ze Yu presented a study of Chinese web novels published on two online platforms, one focused on Chinese language novels, comments and replies, and the other focused on novels (automatically) translated to English and mostly English comments and replies. The comments are found at three levels: at the level of paragraphs (conceptualised as being made during reading), chapters (between reading) and the whole novel (after reading). The English-language platform has a very international audience, while the Chinese-language platform has a mostly Chinese audience. However, topic modelling of the comments shows there are multiple themes shared across the platforms, including discussion of characterisation and story development, reader experience and engagement, cultural references and requests for updates. Platform specific aspects are, for the Chinese-focused platform, culturally specific expressions and references, and for the international platform, discussions of translation quality. One challenge in studying the different readers is that it is difficult to identify their cultural backgrounds. Another is how translation of stories affects readers' perceptions of the story.

Lore de Greve & Gunther Martens - Sizeable expertise? Measuring the focus of professional critics and 'fans' in the online talk of literature

Lore de Greve and Gunter Martens collected reader/viewer reactions to (live) jury discussions in the context of multiple literary prizes and conducted Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA, see link below) to analyse what literary criteria are used by professional critics and lay readers and how their responses evolve over time. The textual responses were annotated according to a classification of literary aspects and entities and sentiment. They found that there are substantial differences between professional and lay critics in how much attention is given to different aspects of the nominated books and the awards, and that this may represent a democratisation of literary criticism and judgement. Finally, they pointed to a limitation common to many social media analyses, which is that non-textual aspects, including emojis, images and videos, are left out of the analysis. The presenters then discussed various examples of multimodal responses and how they can be studied.

Julia Neugarten - The Impact of Fanfiction

Julia Neugarten presented a study of fanfiction of Greek mythology and comments on those fanfiction stories (Neugarten 2024; Neugarten et al. 2024). She defines fanfiction as stories by and for fans, inspired by existing stories, usually exchanged online, for free and they are often transformative (in the sense of ideologically transforming some elements of the original stories). The comments on fanfiction represent a form of reception-within-reception, but they differ from many other forms of reader response. Because the comments have an important performative dimension and are part of a gift economy, they are often not very informative of reading impact. The communities are also strongly normative, leading to almost exclusively positive comments, as there seems to be a consensus that negative comments are not acceptable. This makes interpreting these comments and their relationship to impact challenging. Another challenge is that using machine learning models to automatically annotate sentiment often struggle with

distinguishing between reading experience and character emotion, an aspect of fanfiction that commenters often praise..

Marie-Christine Boucher - Teaching (domain-specific) data literacy for literary studies

Marie-Christine Boucher presented the BiLinked Community of Practice project that develops Open Educational Resources for developing the data literacy skills of university students and teachers. In this presentation, she focused on a lesson that will provide a low-level introduction to quantitative research questions for literary studies through the concept of operationalization and by outlining the kinds of research questions that can be asked when working quantitatively with literary data. One aspect that is not often discussed in the context of research on reading impact is the notion of producing data that can be used beyond a single project, by other scholars with different research questions or for teaching purposes. Furthermore, we should also consider what data literacy is needed to communicate and explain the relevance of our work to society.

Marloes Mak - Individual Differences in Processing, Experiencing and Liking (Stories) - Within the predictive processing framework

In her spotlight talk, Marloes Mak presented her research on investigating the influences of individual differences on reading behaviour. She uses the predictive processing framework—in which perception is influenced by both top-down beliefs and predictions and bottom-up sensory information—to study how gaze duration is affected by lexical features (word characteristics like its length, frequency, concreteness and age of acquisition) and individual level features such as reading skills and exposure to print.

Skilled readers process words faster than average readers (in terms of gaze duration), but the difference between these groups of readers is larger for low-frequency (uncommon) words than for high-frequency words. In other words, top-down processes (e.g. expectations based on reading experience) influence bottom-up processes (perception or gaze duration).

Using the Story World Absorption Scale (SWAS, see Kuijpers et al. 2014) and the Aesthetic-Affective Potential (Jacobs & Kinder 2019), she showed that for readers scoring high on SWAS, there is a positive relationship between gaze duration and the AAP score of a word, whereas for readers scoring low on SWAS, this relationship is negative (Lie et al. 2023). Again, top-down processes (imagination) influences bottom-up processes.

Finally, she showed a relationship between aphantasia—the inability to visualise, or image-free thinking—and how much readers appreciate or like a story and how they score on the SWAS scales. Aphantasia seems to have little impact on liking or appreciating, but leads to lower scores on the SWAS scales, especially Mental Imagery and Transportation.

Shared questions, concepts and challenges

A common methodological theme in various presentations is identifying and categorising online messages, either responses to reading (presentations by Koolen, Yu, de Greve & Martens and Neugarten) or as forms of storytelling (Antoniak). Designing and testing annotation guidelines and gathering annotations is labour intensive, so it could be fruitful to make these more readily available to each other.

Another theme is the use of topic modelling, either of poems (Ceballos Viro) or on reading responses (Yu). There are many different design choices to make in applying these techniques.

A third link is the use of validated scale for capturing reader response, such as the Predictors of Leisure Reading Scale, the Reading Habits Questionnaire and a newly developed Mechanisms of Shared Reading Questionnaire (in the presentation of Ternes) and the Story World Absorption Scale (in the presentation by Mak). The community could benefit both from better awareness of the scales that are available, as well as from seeing the different contexts in which they have been used.

The different presentations show a high number of ways to capture reading response, both during and after reading. This points to the complexity of concepts such as:

- **Story or text:** aspects of the story or text, including characters, plot, narrative, style, level of fictionality, storytelling (as part of broader conversations, see e.g. Antoniak) or as a separate unit.
- **Reading:** this includes different forms of reading, e.g. as an individual or shared activity, in silence or aloud, voluntarily or as part of an assignment or task, as well as the reading medium (paper book or electronic device).
- **Reading context:** the motivation to read (for fun, personal development) and the situational context (at home/school/work or while traveling).
- **Reader:** the influence of culture, life experience, previous reading experience (other texts/stories, other reviews/discussions about a text/story), language
- **Response and Impact:**
 - Impact during reading, immediately after, or long term impact.
 - Impact on individual readers in terms of perception (gaze duration), cognition (comprehension, memory), emotions (muscle movement, verbal expressions), evaluation, attitudes, behaviours, transmission (of stories/texts, see the presentation by Ceballos Viro).
 - Impact on communities/societies: cultural memory, identify and metaphors
- **Response context:** including the platforms or channels used to provide a response, and the conventions and norms of the communities in which the response is situated.
- **Data collection:** the difficulty of capturing all potentially relevant signals of response, be they brain activity, bodily movements, or external responses captured in speech, text, or video. Unobtrusive data capture (data in the wild, not influenced by research design, low control) versus obtrusive data capture (data in the 'lab', shaped by research design, high control)

Many of these concepts have multiple definitions, each of which is relevant and valid in different research contexts for different questions and methods of analysis. This calls for more explicit use of and reference to different definitions, and perhaps a conceptual framework in which to relate the findings from different studies.

Panel Discussions

During the workshop, there were two panel discussions, one on digital social reading, and one on the study of reading impact outside of academia.

Panel discussion 1: Digital Social Reading

Panelists: Lore de Greve, Gunther Martens, Peter Boot and Simone Rebora.

Moderator: Federico Pianzola

Methodological challenges

The panelists perceived a domain-gap, in terms of both data and methods. Not all peers in literary studies consider book reviews, ratings and online discussions worthy of study, but these are part of the phenomena around reading. The application of methods from computer science and machine learning are considered alien to some scholars from different disciplines. Perhaps a more difficult challenge is the multidisciplinary nature of DSR research. How do we make sure that we understand each other?

DSR researchers often talk about communities, but in some contexts, especially book reviews, it is not clear to what extent users of online platforms pay attention to or care about the opinions of others, or have a sense of there being a community. On some platforms or in some contexts this sense of community is clearer than in others. (Lore's example of four literary prizes, one having a very active online community that is strongly connected to the prize and event)

Given the rapid development of online platforms and the integration of online applications and platforms and the physical world, it is difficult what digital social reading will look like in 5 or 10 years.

Digital Social Reading Activities

DSR activities can be interpreted as interactions between users in online contexts, and these interactions exist at many levels. Large platforms can have many large and small communities that partially overlap, but there are also many small websites with only a small group of users who all may know each other personally. There are many book clubs that are fully or partially online or offline.

One aspect to study is how (sub-)communities come about. We usually only become aware of these communities once they exist, but it might be possible to trace their development. Related to this is what happens to a community when it collapses, either because users stop interacting out of their own motivations or because there is sudden change in the technology.

Another aspect is the central interest of the community, that is, what is it that brings them together? This can be a book, author or genre, but it can also be ideological or generational.

Practical aspects

A practical issue is tracing users with accounts on different platforms and connecting their activities. Their interactions across multiple accounts provide a more complete picture of their DSR activities and their reading responses.

The rapid development of multilingual language models makes it easier to study DSR across different languages, including languages that the researcher knows. Models are also better at understanding jokes, irony and sarcasm, as well as more nuanced aspects of literary criticism.

A particular practical challenge is that companies behind large platforms regularly change the technology or the accessibility, usually in the direction of less openness and increasing monetisation. This can have big consequences for what data we can collect and study.

Ethical and legal issues

The EU directive on using public data for research gives us a lot of elbow room in terms of legal issues of intellectual property rights, but we quickly run into ethical issues. There are many technical solutions to anonymise data, but this works only to a limited extent. There are also many techniques for de-anonymisation that undo that.

Moreover, the level of anonymisation is inversely related to how much we can do with the data, especially for studying individual differences and relating them to characteristics of individual readers. When budgeting for a project, it is useful to allot some of that budget for legal or ethical advice. Also, as a community of researchers on reading impact, we should train ourselves in getting ethical approval beforehand, which is already the norm in some disciplines, such as psychology.

There are examples where reaching out to platforms to ask for data or to collaborate has been successful. Being transparent about our research interests and intentions may make platforms more responsive.

Panel discussion 2: Reader Response in the Real World

Panelists: Gwena Jaouen, Manon Beentjes, Daan Beeke

Expertise of the panelists

Daan Beeke

Daan Beeke works at Stichting Lezen, an organization that promotes reading and supports research on reading. Daan is a teacher himself and specializes in students aged 12-18. He is also active in the EURead platform, which serves as a bridge between scientific knowledge about reading³ and real-world applications.

Daan presented a platform he has worked on: www.hebbanindeklas.nl, which is used in schools for reading promotion and book evaluation. In this platform, students within a class form a small online reviewers' community, where they can recommend books to each other. The platform collects data on students' activity, which is not publicly available but can be accessed on demand for scientific research.

Gwena Jaouen

Gwena Jaouen has extensive experience working with recommendation systems across different fields. She initially worked on music recommendation systems at the very beginning of the digitalization of the music industry. Later, she collaborated extensively with publishers and other stakeholders in the book industry, including the WPG Group and NBD Biblion, focusing on bookstores and libraries.

Gwena conducted empirical research to explore what motivates people to choose one book over another. As part of this study, she conducted 20 in-depth interviews and developed five reader profiles, taking into account various factors that influence decision-making, such as mood and context. The identified profiles are: Escapist/Daydreamer; Story Sharer; Focused Knowledge Seeker; Well-Read Explorer; Trend-Sensitive Reader. Based on these profiles, books can be recommended in a more personalized way.

Manon Beentjes

Manon Beentjes is a young bookfluencer who posts short videos (2-3 minutes) about books she has read. She has almost 10K followers on TikTok, which is a significant number, and she creates 3-4 videos per week, making her content production quite intensive.

Manon exclusively reads and promotes books she has personally chosen, primarily in the genres of romance, fantasy, and romantasy. While some of these books are written in Dutch, many are in English. She prefers not to post about "problematic" authors.

³ Such as the (Dutch) reports of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), see <https://www.pisa-nederland.nl/resultaten/> and <https://www.pisa-nederland.nl/resultaten2022/>

Reading promotion at school

During the panel discussion, reading promotion at schools was addressed. Various factors play a role in fostering a reading culture at school. Much depends on teachers, who should set an example by being readers themselves. However, other factors also influence reading popularity, such as the availability of books (a nearby library or books in the classroom) and the tension between required reading for school and students' personal reading preferences.

The platform hebbanindeklas.nl was also discussed. Daan Beeke argued that peer recommendations work well for school children, whereas Tina pointed out that some pupils might prefer the anonymity of the internet over the opinions and scrutiny of their peers. This question could serve as a strong starting point for empirical research, as the platform provides valuable data for both qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Social media

A major topic of this panel was social media and its role in reading promotion. While social media can be a powerful tool, there are also some drawbacks.

First, publishers, despite their efforts to engage with readers on social media, often struggle to build a real connection because they are not accustomed to being active promoters.

Second, books promoted on social media are very often published in English, which poses a challenge. English versions of books tend to be more popular than Dutch ones on these platforms for several reasons: some topics sound more natural or fluent in English, and English books are often cheaper. Additionally, they are an integral part of the cozy reading aesthetic that is widely marketed online.

Third, book promotion through social media—particularly on platforms like TikTok (BookTok)—is sometimes criticized for shortening attention spans, especially among schoolchildren who may struggle to focus on longer texts. Social media is frequently blamed for the decline in attention spans among younger generations. However, BookTok videos can also serve as an initial motivation for reading, making them an effective promotional tool despite these concerns.

A shared roadmap

We worked towards a shared roadmap. Although we started with shared research questions, in the discussions they got pushed to the background and the roadmap elements focused on community aspects, such as making inventories of concepts, datasets and research questions.

Vocabulary Activities

During the workshop we had two sessions on establishing a shared vocabulary. In the first session, small groups each picked one of four core concepts and discussed definitions and related concepts. Also, we did a plenary inventory of relevant concepts.

- Impact (appreciation, cognition, transformation, ...)
 - Dimensions:
 - Momentary vs. lasting impact: feeling/emotion in the moment
 - Direct vs. indirect: while reading, or reflective through writing a review or through discussing with others (impact after the fact)
 - Personal
 - cognitive (e.g. memory, comprehension)
 - behavioural
 - affective (e.g. appreciation, admiration, identity-forming)
 - Societal
 - cultural memory
 - cultural identity
 - cultural metaphor
 - Transformation: change in perception or attitude towards something
- Response: how to measure without falling into the trap of “response bias” (people self-reporting) → physiological response: Judith Beck, Freiburg (study of sub-vocalisation: the process of silently pronouncing words in one's mind while reading”) via laryngeal muscles (but what about anauralia: no inner voice); reading vs. self-paced reading
- Reception: a very general term that includes responses; responses can be physical, mental, in spoken or written words. Which of these are measurable in a useful way? How to also account for social, cultural and historical context?
- Reading (individual/group/being read to, quiet/out loud, written/audio,, ...)
- Narrative, storytelling
- Story:
 - Characters
 - Style
 - Plot
 - Motifs and/or themes
- Reader (age, level of literacy, level of fluency, origin/culture, professional/amateur)
- participation framework/structure
- evaluation (stance/appraisal)
- Fictionality
- Literariness
- Identity, gender and other categories
- Performativity
- Classification, Categorisation, transtextuality, genres, high- and low-brow literature
- Motivation
- Marketing, money
- Situatedness, communicative settings (for reading, filling in questionnaires, writing book reviews, etc.)
- Translation, adaptation, negotiation of meaning

In the second session, we asked participants what would be a good way to develop and share this vocabulary. Multiple groups came up with similar suggestions:

- Create an easy-to-maintain site for a shared vocabulary/lexicon, similar to The Turing Way (<https://book.the-turing-way.org>), the living handbook of narratology (<https://www-archiv.fdm.uni-hamburg.de/lhn/>) or the Lexicon of Scholarly Editing (LexiconSE, <https://lexiconse.uantwerpen.be/lexicon/>)
- Think about ways to manage connections and contradictions between concepts, using network (e.g. using ontologies and semantic web framework)
- Use sub-definitions for concepts with multiple definitions.
- Involve the entire CLS / ELS community, but start with a small dedicated group to get it off the ground.
- Collect all definitions (including ones already published) so researchers can look up and cite definitions they use.
- Connect concepts with actual research (both work that theorises or defines them and work that uses them). Given the enormous amount of work for the latter, it is necessary to involve the entire community.
- Think about rewards (publication beyond Zenodo?).

Research Question Overlap

For an initial session on overlap of research questions (Monday afternoon) we split up in groups. The discussions in the four groups took very different directions. No clear pattern emerged.

Research Questions that were mentioned included:

- What are the underlying mental processes connected to reading leading to different types of output, versions of appreciation in different forms?
- What affect is left in the wake of reading texts?
- How does the impact of fiction depend on the fiction and on the reader? (leaving aside social factors on the macro level for the moment, although micro social influences can be studied through this data sometimes).
- Is there a correlation of high-brow/low-brow literary quality and a measure of immersion/immersiveness?
- What is the role of education and reading experiences in educational settings on reading behaviour, concepts of reading, academic success?

Some potential approaches to these questions:

- to focus on the particular type of texts that are perhaps more structured, or where the structures are more easily recognizable, because it stabilizes one of the variables. The fanfiction genre e.g. would meet this criterion of repetition or shared structures in some way;
- working across data types, multimodality: processing reader reviews/response via multiple channels.

Some challenges in researching these questions were also mentioned:

- Conceptual: Difficulty of defining terms/translating concepts into different languages
- Also conceptual: What is the object of reading: a text or a story? What is the role of style/stylistics?
- Community: Difficulty of finding each other (due to use of different terms?)
- Technological: Limits of technology
- Material: Preservation of materials (what is the focus/metadata?)
- Methodological: Loss of elements and compromise, reduction of complexity

Break-out session on methods and on data

There were various breakout sessions on methods and data.

Tuesday morning

The first session opposed two broad methods of study: empirical methods and computational methods. A third breakout group looked at the theoretical grounding for these methods. The empirical methods group presented various data sources, the available measures or methods (grouped under physiological, self-report and observational methods), some challenges and solutions for these challenges. The computational methods group made a first distinction between explorative and hypothesis-driven research and created a list of tools/technologies. As to challenges, the group made a distinction between challenges at the tool level (e.g. tools that have been trained on newspapers being really unsuitable for the domain of literature) and challenges at the discipline level (e.g. lack of communication between different fields). The group that discussed theoretical grounding posed some fundamental questions, such as 'What are text-intrinsic features?', 'What is a narrative?' and 'Why do we need theory if we have machine learning?'.

Tuesday afternoon

In this session we discussed five questions. For each question we report some key aspects from the discussion.

1. Which methodological gaps do we need to fill to face existing challenges in literary research?
Key aspects: the difference between lay and professional readers; the choice we may have to make for a particular perspective if we want to do interdisciplinary research; whether there is room for meta-methodological research (e.g. comparison of assumptions).
2. Which data can we use?
Key aspects: everything that is ethically available; existing data can be reused; prepare for reuse (methodologically and legally); room for (AI) simulated data.
3. How is empirical literary research similar to computational literary research and how do they differ?
Key aspects: scale; scholarly culture; paradigm; exploration vs. hypothesis

4. How can we discover the connection between literary texts and the response to them?
Key aspects: what is the text (objective/subjective/social); types of responses; ecological validity; triangulation of methods.
5. How can research on literature highlight the challenges within CS?
Key aspects: challenge of prompt writing for AI; challenge of interpretation of AI output; answering fuzzy and subjective questions; appropriateness of personalisation; working with missing data.

Wednesday afternoon

In this data breakout session we split into three groups that each discussed two different types of data. For each group again we mention some key aspects of the discussion.

1. Empirical vs. naturalistic data
Key aspects: how natural is naturalistic data; empirical data (e.g. brain scans) also need interpretation; the necessity and acceptability of averaging over individuals; usefulness of annotation vs. LLMs.
2. Survey vs. naturalistic data
Key aspects: data bias (in both types); AI generated reviews; observation is always guided by theory; data about children; missing data.
3. Synthetic vs. naturalistic data
Key aspects: discussed collection, analysis and reuse of data. Differences in transparency; aspects of context; ethics and legal aspects; how to evaluate synthetic data.

Preparing the Roadmap

There were two sessions where we explicitly worked towards a roadmap. During the preparation of the workshop, we discussed whether it would be useful to show some examples of a roadmap or to provide an abstract structure. We decided against that, as we didn't want to limit the group's creativity.

In the first session, on Tuesday afternoon, the participants worked in groups of increasing size. There were three 'roadmaps' that resulted from this:

- a map that was basically a model of the domain of reading and its context: the book, the world, the reader and reading output, centered around the act of reading;
- a list of ingredients (questions, tools, concepts, etc) of the research process, roughly grouped into research stages (research questions, operationalisation, tooling, publication);
- A visual representation of four aspects of the research process: data, methods, tools + theories and community, connected by highways.

In the second session, on Thursday morning, we tried to merge the roadmaps from Tuesday's session. This proved very difficult. Discussions tended to focus on practical infrastructural steps, such as creating inventories of definitions, tools, researchers and research questions. There were some differences in approach between those for whom a roadmap had to contain clear steps and those for whom a roadmap had to give a high-level overview of the field.

Reflection and future steps

At the end of the workshop, in a plenary discussion, participants were asked to reflect on what they learned, what they thought of the workshop and whether they think another workshop would be useful.

Several participants emphasised that the workshop showed the value of thinking about our individual research contributions as being part of a collaborative effort. There was broad consensus that there is value in working on shared inventories and establishing ways to communicate and share research output, datasets and ideas. This would allow us to keep informed of developments and research designs and datasets that can be reused.

The format of the workshop, combining short presentations with many highly interactive sessions, was deemed very effective and useful for future events. Several participants stressed that, in the future, it would be beneficial to schedule more time during the workshop for working on deliverables, such as creating an inventory or developing a more complete, publishable roadmap.

Suggestions for concrete future steps included:

- Writing a workshop report.
- Developing an inventory of shared concepts and definitions, tracing the history of terms.
- Choosing or setting up a channel or platform for communication and exchange.
- Organising follow up events, in the form of similar workshops. One suggestion was to use conferences and other annual events that many of us attend to organise satellite meetings.
- Working on acquiring grants and funding for future meetings. Some sources might be considered, including:
 - ZIF Bielefeld has various schemes to support shorter or long-term cooperation (<https://fundit.fr/en/calls/research-groups-zif-bielefeld>). This would allow for multiple research visits over the course of a few years, each workshop building on the result of the other. Simone Rebora, Silvia Lilli, Álvaro Ceballos Viro and Marloes Mak proposed to start drafting an application for a series of meetings.
 - Dagstuhl offers seminars similar to the Lorentz Center (<https://www.dagstuhl.de/en/seminars/dagstuhl-seminars>). Applications are for a single event of multiple days.
 - The Dutch research school for literary studies (OSL) has a research incubator grant (<https://www.oslit.nl/osl-research-incubator-2024/>) meant to support meetings.
 - Also from the Netherlands, there is the KNAW Early Career Partnerships grant, designed to support interdisciplinary meetings (<https://www.knaw.nl/en/funds-and-prizes/knaw-early-career-partnerships>).
 - COST Action (<https://www.cost.eu>). Similar to ZIF schemes for long-term cooperation, this could support multiple events over several years.

- Considerations for the organisation of follow-up workshops:
 - Make sure there are not only sessions dedicated to presentation and discussion, but also sessions to focus on writing and creating inventories (of terms, research questions, etc.)
 - We should take care that PhD students can be involved.
- Topics for such follow-up workshops could be (ideally we'd have a tentative program for a series of, say, five workshops):
 - Making an inventory of relevant vocabulary, definitions and theories, including for terms that are “shared” but used differently in different research projects.
 - Making an inventory of scales and measures related to reader response (e.g. questionnaires)
 - Discuss possibilities to create benchmarks for evaluating computational techniques for e.g. identifying or annotating aspects of reader response and impact in research data.
 - Discuss the possibility and value of developing a shared question or shared task. During this workshop, the notion of a shared task was questioned, as it is not clear what a meaningful shared task could be. In Computer Science this is used to refer to a task where the desired result is specified beforehand, and all participating teams or individuals work towards reaching that result. Does it make sense to speak of a shared task or question if different participants address different aspects of the task or question?
- Establish communication channels specifically for sub-groups interested in common topics. There are a few vehicles that could be used for this purpose, e.g.:
 - The Discourse server for the IGEL society (<https://discourse.igelsociety.org>), which is not very active at the moment, but we can discuss in what ways we can best use it to actively share resources.
 - A Zenodo community could be created, where anyone can publish relevant materials, which are then easily discoverable via the community (the main community page links to individual publications, which links back to the community page). Options for such publication are a list of key terms and definitions and this workshop report.
 - The IGEL society also has supported the formation of 21 research coalitions within the community. These coalitions are small groups of 3-8 researchers concerned with specific topics in empirical studies of literature, working together to prepare publications, training material or events on their research topic. One of such coalition groups is devoted to the topic of “computational stylistics” (<https://igelsociety.org/research-coalitions/#computational-stylistics>) and could be used as a venue for future (annual) meetings and continuous communication. We could consider joining them and/or proposing a new coalition group.
 - The PALA association is also open for the formation of SIGs (special interest groups), with similar strategies to the IGEL research coalitions. One of such SIGs is devoted to the topic of “corpus stylistics” (<https://www.pala.ac.uk/corpus-stylistics.html>). We could consider joining them and/or proposing a new coalition group.

Finally, as concrete outcomes of the Impressed by Reading workshop, we, as the organisers, promised to deliver the present report and publish it via Zenodo. We also promised to create a Zenodo community, where the participants of this workshop can join. The community will also be open for scholars interested in any aspect of computational literary studies. Through Impressed by Reading, we hope to have launched the beginning of fruitful future collaborations.

Links to Code and Data

Testing text analysis methods for literary-historical corpora:

<https://github.com/GhentCDH/CLSinfra>

StorySeeker: <https://github.com/maria-antoniak/storyseeker>

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